

CALCULATION MODELS AND CONSTITUTIVE EQUATIONS OF COMPOSITES WITH TWO OR THREE DIMENSIONAL WAVY FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

In the present paper, three kinds of fiber arrangements, called as the iso-phase, random-phase and the multi-phase models for two dimensional composites with arbitrary wavy fibers, were discussed. Their calculation models were proposed and their constitutive equations derived based on the traditional laminate theory on considering variations of local fiber volume fraction. Then, these models were developed to the composite with three dimensional wavy fibers, respectively. Their constitutive equations were also derived based upon the generalized Hooke's theory for three dimensional orthotropic material. It was found that three dimensional calculation models could be reduced to two dimensional ones.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composites with wavy fiber in them, for example, the fabric composites, usually show very complex stress-strain behavior as compared with the straight fiber composites. For this reason, many simplified models have been introduced for predicting the effects of fiber waviness and arrangements on the nonlinear elastic behaviors. For two dimensional problems, two kinds of fiber arrangement, iso-phase and random-phase models, were proposed and several experimental attempts, such as the photoelastic tests, have been carried out. So far, mechanical behaviors of two dimensional wavy fiber composites have been studied in detail both theoretically and experimentally [1-5]. However, general models for both two dimensional (2D) and three dimensional (3D) wavy fiber problems of utmost importance, especially in thick-section laminates and three dimensional textile structural composites, have been left unsolved [6].

This paper deals with general calculation models for composites with 2D or 3D continuous fibers of arbitrary waviness and arbitrary arrangements. At first, geometrical relations related to fiber waviness is considered. Then, for two dimensional problems, several general calculation models will be proposed and their constitutive equations derived based upon traditional laminate theory. At last, the models for two dimensional composites are developed to composites with three dimensional wavy fibers based upon the generalized Hooke's law for 3D orthotropic materials. For convenience, only elastic properties are discussed in the present paper.

2. GEOMETRIC RELATIONS

2.1 Fiber Shape

For generality, fiber shape is expressed by the expansion of Fourier series to represent the arbitrary waviness. In the xyz coordinates, for two dimensional wavy fiber problems, fiber shape can be written as follows:

$$y = f(x) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(a_n \cos \frac{2\pi nx}{\lambda} + b_n \sin \frac{2\pi nx}{\lambda} \right) \tag{1}$$

For 3D wavy fiber problems, fiber shape of arbitrary waviness can be given by:

$$y=f(x)=\frac{a_0}{2}+\sum_{n=1}^{\infty}\left(a_n\cos\frac{2\pi nx}{\lambda}+b_n\sin\frac{2\pi nx}{\lambda}\right)$$

$$z=g(x)=\frac{c_0}{2}+\sum_{n=1}^{\infty}\left(c_n\cos\frac{2\pi nx}{\lambda}+d_n\sin\frac{2\pi nx}{\lambda}\right) \tag{2}$$

where a_n, b_n, c_n and d_n are the coefficients of the Fourier series and λ is the wavelength of the wavy fiber, $0 < \lambda < \infty$. It is easy to see that the sinusoidal shaped fiber and helical fiber [1-4,10,11] are typical examples of them.

2.2 FIBER VOLUME FRACTION

In comparison with the fiber volume fraction V_{f0} of straight fiber composites, the local fiber volume fraction V_f of the composite with wavy fibers of the same fiber interval, can be derived from Figure 1 under the same representative unit volume, ABCDA'B'C'D'.

$$V_f = \frac{A_0 ds}{ABCD A' B' C' D'} = \frac{A_0 dx}{ABCD A' B' C' D'} \sqrt{1+(f'(x))^2+(g'(x))^2} = V_{f0} \sqrt{1+(f'(x))^2+(g'(x))^2} \tag{3}$$

It can be seen that V_f is a function of the inclination of wavy fibers. Further, the average fiber volume fraction over one cycle is given by:

$$\bar{V}_f = \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda V_f dx = \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda \left(V_{f0} \sqrt{1+(f'(x))^2+(g'(x))^2} \right) dx = (S/\lambda) V_{f0} \tag{4}$$

The above relations can be easily reduced to 2D wavy fiber problems [5,10]. In this paper, local fiber volume fraction, V_f [5,7,10,11], is employed in deriving equations of all the models instead of average fiber volume fraction, V_f [1-4].

2.3 Constitutive Relations of 3D Off-axis Unidirectional Composites

Figure 2 is an illustration of a 3D off-axis unidirectional composite in $oxyz$ coordinates which is usually modeled as **3D orthotropic materials**. Here, x' axis is determined to be always in the fiber axial direction. For this composite, relations between stress and strain components under rotation of coordinate systems from $oxyz$ to $ox'y'z'$ can be expressed as [8,9]:

Fig.1 Inclined fiber segment and local fiber volume fraction V_f

Fig.2 Coordinate systems for 3D unidirectional composite

$$\{\sigma\}_{x'y'z'} = [T_\sigma] \{\sigma\}_{xyz} \tag{5} \quad \{\epsilon\}_{x'y'z'} = [T_\epsilon] \{\epsilon\}_{xyz} \tag{6}$$

where $[T_\sigma]$ and $[T_\epsilon]$ are the transformation matrices for the stress and strain components, respectively. They are determined by direction cosines of straight fibers of the above composite in xyz coordinates. For wavy fiber composites, direction cosines of each fiber segment can be obtained from Eqn (1) and (2). Furthermore, relations between the on-axis (in $x'y'z'$) and off-axis

(in xyz) stiffness matrices of the **3D orthotropic material** by rotating coordinate systems, can be given by [9]:

$$[Q_{ij}^*]=[T_{\epsilon}]^T[Q_{ij}][T_{\epsilon}] \quad (7) \quad \text{and,} \quad [S_{ij}^*]=[T_{\sigma}]^T[S_{ij}][T_{\sigma}] \quad (8)$$

where, $[S_{ij}]=[Q_{ij}]^{-1}$, $[S_{ij}^*]=[Q_{ij}^*]^{-1}$ ($i,j=1,2,\dots,6$) (9)
 $[Q_{ij}]$ and $[S_{ij}]$ are the stiffness and compliant matrices of **3D orthotropic materials** in $x'y'z'$ coordinates, respectively. They are determined by engineering constants of the composite [8,9].
 $[Q_{ij}^*]$ and $[S_{ij}^*]$ are the off-axis stiffness and compliant matrices in xyz coordinate, respectively.

3.TWO DIMENSIONAL WAVY FIBER PROBLEMS

3.1 Iso-phase Model

The iso-phase model is defined as that all the wavy fibers are in phase along the x direction and have the same interval between each other, as shown in Figure 3 [10].

Figure 3 Illustration of Iso-phase model

In this model, each volume element of the composite in the infinitesimal interval, dx , can be modeled as an off-axis straight fiber laminae, as can be seen from Fig.3 (b). Then, the constitutive relations for the off-axis laminae of the infinitesimal volume in dx , can be obtained:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{s}_{11} & \bar{s}_{12} & \bar{s}_{16} \\ \bar{s}_{12} & \bar{s}_{22} & \bar{s}_{26} \\ \bar{s}_{16} & \bar{s}_{26} & \bar{s}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Here, S_{ij} are the components of compliant matrix of the off-axis laminae [1-3].

Under uniaxial tension, σ_x , it can be obtained:

$$\epsilon_x = \bar{S}_{11} \sigma_x, \quad \epsilon_y = \bar{S}_{12} \sigma_x, \quad \gamma_{xy} = \bar{S}_{16} \sigma_x \quad (11)$$

Thus, the average tensile strain, ϵ_x , is given by:

$$\bar{\epsilon}_x = \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda \epsilon_x dx \quad (12)$$

Substituting Eqn (11) into Eqn (10) and expanding it, it can be obtained:

$$\bar{\epsilon}_x = \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda \bar{S}_{11} \sigma_x dx = \frac{\sigma_x}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda \{S_{11} \cos^4 \theta + S_{22} \sin^4 \theta + (2S_{12} + S_{66}) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta\} dx \quad (13)$$

Note that because S_{ij} of a infinitesimal volume are functions of local fiber volume fraction, V_f , the calculation of the integral in Eqn (13) becomes very complex and usually numerical methods are employed [5,10].

Further, the effective Young's modulus in the x -direction can be obtained from Eqn (13):

$$E_x^* = \sigma_x / \bar{\epsilon}_x = \left[\frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda \{S_{11} \cos^4 \theta + S_{22} \sin^4 \theta + (2S_{12} + S_{66}) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta\} dx \right]^{-1} \quad (14)$$

3.2 Random-Phase Model

The random-phase model is defined as the model in which all fibers are uniformly random-distributed and can be shown in the Figure 4. The spatial position of fiber in the xyz coordinate system can be expressed by:

$$y = f(x-d) \tag{15}$$

Figure 4 Illustration of random-phase model

where d is the translation of the fiber in the x -direction. In random-phase model, d ($0 \leq d \leq \lambda$) is assumed to be uniform-randomly distributed in the x -direction. From the definition, it can be seen that each fiber segment in a fiber over a single cycle has the same probability of existing in each infinitesimal volume in the x -direction. Thus, each infinitesimal volume in dx , has the same properties with the whole composite. In this model, each fiber segment in infinitesimal volume can be treated as an off-axis laminae with inclination angle θ_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, \text{infinite}$) [5,10] and the infinitesimal volume in dx treated as a laminate being composed of these laminas under the uniform strain condition.

For a inclined fiber segment, its stress - strain relations can be expressed by:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \tag{16}$$

where Q_{ij} are the components of stiffness matrix of the off-axis laminae [1-3].

Applying the laminate theory to the infinitesimal volume in dx , its stress - strain relations, which are just the same for the whole composite, can be obtained:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{16} \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{26} \\ C_{16} & C_{26} & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \tag{17}$$

where

$$C_{mn} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda \bar{Q}_{mn} dx \quad (m, n = 1, 2, 6) \tag{18}$$

Inverting Eqn (17), it can be obtained:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11}^* & S_{12}^* & S_{16}^* \\ S_{12}^* & S_{22}^* & S_{26}^* \\ S_{16}^* & S_{26}^* & S_{66}^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \tag{19}$$

where $[S_{mn}^*] = [C_{mn}]^{-1}$ is the compliant matrix of the infinitesimal volume [1-3].

Under the uni-directional tension, σ_x , it can be obtained:

$$\epsilon_x = S_{11}^* \sigma_x \tag{20}$$

Then, the effective longitudinal Young's modulus is :

$$E_X^* = 1/S_{11}^* \tag{21}$$

3.3 Multi-phase Model

Another arrangement in which fibers are perfectly random distributed in x-direction is shown in Figure 5. We define this model as "Multi-phase model" [5,10]. Here, the spatial position of the fibers can be represented by:

$$y = f(x-d_j) \quad (0 \leq d_j \leq \lambda) \quad (22)$$

Figure 5 Illustration of Multi-phase model

Similarly to the previous section, the infinitesimal volume in dx can be treated as a laminate being composed of i laminas which has inclination angle θ_i ($i=1,2,\dots,p$; p :integer). For the infinitesimal volume in dx , the stress - strain relation is given by:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11}^* & C_{12}^* & C_{16}^* \\ C_{12}^* & C_{22}^* & C_{26}^* \\ C_{16}^* & C_{26}^* & C_{66}^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

$$C_{mn}^* = \sum_{j=1}^p k_j \bar{Q}_{mn}(\theta_j) \quad (i=1,2, \dots p, m,n=1,2,6, 0 \leq k_j \leq 1) \quad (24)$$

where

p is an integer and k_j is the ratio of the number of translated parts of fibers to the number of total fibers. $\bar{Q}_{mn}(\theta_i)$ are the components of stiffness matrix of an off-axis lamina shown in Eqn (16).

The inversion of Eqn (23) is given by:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11}^\# & S_{12}^\# & S_{16}^\# \\ S_{12}^\# & S_{22}^\# & S_{26}^\# \\ S_{16}^\# & S_{26}^\# & S_{66}^\# \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

Here, $[S_{mn}^\#]$ and $[S_{mn}^*]$ in Eqn (19) have the same form but different values.

Under the uniaxial tension, σ_x , it can be obtained:

$$\epsilon_x = S_{11}^\# \sigma_x \quad (26)$$

Then, the average strain ϵ_x and the effective longitudinal Young's modulus can be obtained:

$$\bar{\epsilon}_x = \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda \epsilon_x dx = \frac{\sigma_x}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda S_{11}^\# dx \quad (27)$$

$$E_x^\# = \frac{\sigma_x}{\bar{\epsilon}_x} = \left[\frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda S_{11}^\# dx \right]^{-1} \quad (28)$$

4. THREE DIMENSIONAL WAVY FIBER PROBLEMS

4.1 Iso-phase Model

The 3D iso-phase model is an extreme case of fiber arrangements defined as that all the wavy fibers are arranged in the same phase as shown in Figure 6 [10-11]. In this model, each

infinitesimal element dx can be modeled as a 3D off-axis unidirectional composite-3D orthotropic material as shown in Fig.2. Therefore, the constitutive equation of dx_i can be given by:

$$\{\epsilon\}_{xyz}^{(i)} = [S_{mn}^*]^{(i)} \{\sigma\}_{xyz} \quad (29)$$

where, $m, n=1, 2, \dots, 6$, and $[S_{mn}^*]^{(i)}$ is in the same form with Eqn (8).

Under the uniaxial tension, σ_x , strain components of dx_i in xyz coordinates can be obtained:

$$\epsilon_{xyz}^{(i)} = S_{m1}^* \sigma_x \quad (30)$$

For the whole composite, therefore, the average strain in the x -direction, $\bar{\epsilon}_x$, and the **effective longitudinal Young's modulus** can be obtained under the **uniform stress condition**:

$$\bar{\epsilon}_x = \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda \epsilon_x^{(i)} dx = \frac{\sigma_x}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda S_{11}^* dx \quad (31)$$

$$\bar{E}_x = \sigma_x / \bar{\epsilon}_x = \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda S_{11}^* dx \right)^{-1} \quad (32)$$

4.2 Random-phase Model

The random-phase model is another extreme case of fiber arrangements as depicted in Figure 7.

Fig. 6 Illustration of iso-phase model for the composite with 3D wavy fibers

Fig. 7 Illustration of random-phase model for the composite with 3D wavy fibers

The spatial position of a wavy fiber can be expressed by:

$$\begin{cases} y = f(x - d) \\ z = g(x - d) \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

where d is the translation of a wavy fiber in x -direction, and $0 \leq d \leq \lambda$. The definition of 3D random-phase model is the same with the 2D random-phase model. Thus, each fiber segment in one wavy period has the same probability of existing in each infinitesimal element dx_i , and so, orientations of fiber segments in dx_i is uniform-randomly distributed. Consequently, all the infinitesimal elements vertical to x axis have the same mechanical properties with the whole composite.

In this model, it is reasonable to treat each unit cell with a fiber segment as a 3D off-axis unidirectional composite, just as shown in Fig.2. Thus, the infinitesimal element dx can be modeled as a composite being composed of all these composites under the **uniform strain condition** [10, 11]. Therefore, the stress - strain relation of dx_i can be obtained as follows:

$$\{\sigma\}_{xyz} = [C_{mn}] \{\epsilon\}_{xyz} \quad (34)$$

where,

$$C_{mn} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda Q_{mnj}^* dx_i \quad (35)$$

$Q^{*(i)}_{mnj}$ are the components of off-axis stiffness matrix of the unit cell with the j th inclined fiber segment in dx_i which is in the same form with Eqn (7). In random-phase model, the shape of fibers being axial symmetric or point-wise symmetric in one wavy period, will cause all the coupling components to zero. Helical wavy fiber is a typical example.

From Eqn (34), the constitutive relation for the whole composite can be obtained:

$$\{\epsilon\}_{xyz} = [S^{#mn}] \{\sigma\}_{xyz} \quad (36) \quad \text{where,} \quad [S^{#mn}] = [Cmn]^{-1} \quad (37)$$

$[S^{#mn}]$ is the compliant matrix of the whole composite.

Under the uniaxial tension, σ_x , strain components in xyz coordinates can be given :

$$\epsilon_{xyx} = S^{#m1} \sigma_x \quad (38)$$

Thus, the **effective longitudinal Young's modulus** of the whole composite is:

$$\bar{E}_x = E_x^{(i)} = S_{11}^{#-1} \quad (39)$$

4.3 Multi-phase Model

Another most general fiber arrangement - the multi-phase model is depicted in Figure 8. The spatial position of wavy fibers can be expressed by Eqn (40).

Fig.8 Illustration of multi-phase model for the composite with 3D wavy fibers

$$\begin{cases} y = f(x-di) \\ z = g(x-di) \end{cases} \quad (40)$$

Where d_i is the translation of a wavy fiber in the x -direction, and d_i for all the fibers is perfectly random distributed, $0 \leq d_i \leq \lambda$. Thus, each fiber segment in one wavy period usually does not have the same probability of existing in one infinitesimal element dx_i , and so, in dx_i there are multi-phases of fibers. Consequently, mechanical properties of each infinitesimal element dx_i as shown in Fig.8 are usually different from each other.

Similarly to the random phase model, each unit cell with a fiber segment in dx_i can be treated as a 3D off-axis unidirectional composite and its constitutive equation can be given in the same form with Eqn (8). Therefore, each infinitesimal element dx_i can be treated as a composite being composed of all the 3D off-axis composites of unit cells with out phased fiber segments under the **uniform strain condition**. Thus, its stress - strain relation can be given by:

$$\{\sigma\}^{(i)}_{xyz} = [C^*_{mn}]^{(i)} \{\varepsilon\}^{(i)}_{xyz} \quad (41) \quad \text{where,} \quad C^*_{mn}{}^{(i)} = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} k_j Q^*_{mnj}{}^{(i)} \quad (42)$$

$$i=1,2,\dots,\infty, \quad j=1,2,\dots,p, \quad 0 \leq k_i \leq 1, \quad \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} k_i = 1$$

k_j is the ratio of the number of the j th inclined fiber to all fibers. Q^*_{mnj} are the components of off-axis stiffness matrix of the unit cell with the j th inclined fiber segment which is in the similar form to Eqn (7). By inverting Eqn (41), we obtained:

$$\{\varepsilon\}^{(i)}_{xyz} = [S^{**}_{mn}]^{(i)} \{\sigma\}^{(i)}_{xyz} \quad (43) \quad \text{where,} \quad [S^{**}_{mn}]^{(i)} = [C^*_{mn}]^{(i)-1} \quad (44)$$

$[S^{**}_{mn}]^{(i)}$ is the compliant matrix of the infinitesimal element dx_i .

Under the uniaxial tension, σ_x , strain components of dx_i in xyx coordinates can be obtained:

$$\varepsilon^{(i)}_{xyz} = S^{**}_{m1}{}^{(i)} \sigma_x \quad (45)$$

For the whole composite, therefore, the constitutive equation can be obtained, similarly to the 3D iso-phase model, by combining the constitutive equations of all the dx_i over one wavy period in x -direction under the **uniform stress condition**:

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_x = \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda \varepsilon_x^{(i)} dx = \frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda S^{**}_{11}{}^{(i)} \sigma_x dx = \frac{\sigma_x}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda S^{**}_{11}{}^{(i)} dx \quad (46)$$

Then, the **effective longitudinal Young's modulus** can be obtained:

$$\bar{E}_x = \sigma_x / \bar{\varepsilon}_x = \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} \int_0^\lambda S^{**}_{11}{}^{(i)} dx \right)^{-1} \quad (47)$$

5. CONCLUSIONS

(1) The mechanical properties of composites with 2D or 3D arbitrary wavy fibers could be specified by three calculation models respectively, called as iso-phase, random-phase and multi-phase models corresponding to the spatial arrangements of wavy fibers.

(2) The constitutive equations of these models were derived based upon traditional laminate theory and generalized Hooke's law for 3D orthotropic materials, respectively.

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